

Effective Longitudinal Shear Modulus of Unidirectional Composites

D. J. Lee, T. H. Jeong and H. G. Kim*
Dept. of Mechanical Engineering
Yeungnam University
Gyungsan, Korea 712-749

ABSTRACT

Longitudinal shear modulus of continuous fiber-reinforced composites is predicted using theoretical and numerical analysis methods that based on a concept of unit cell. In this paper, circular, hexagonal and rectangular shapes of reinforced fiber are considered. And the fiber spatial distribution is rectangular and hexagonal array. The predicted moduli correlate well with the experimental results that obtained by a modified iosipescu shear test(IST), and several proposed predictions. It is found that the rectangular fiber shape in lower fiber volume fraction and the circular fiber shape in high fiber volume fraction show the higher longitudinal shear modulus. Also, the rectangular array has a higher longitudinal shear modulus than the hexagonal one.

INTRODUCTION

Polymeric composites with a laminated and fibrous structure have a typical shortcoming - their low shear resistance, especially in planes where the properties of the material are determined by the matrix. Therefore, various methods have been proposed which estimate the overall elastic shear moduli as well as the bounds for effective elastic response in terms of the elastic properties of the constituent phases of the composites[1-6]. Especially, the longitudinal shear modulus of unidirectional composites has been studied by several researcher [7-11]. Hashin[8] obtained the upper and lower bounds for actual unidirectional composites by a variation method and Nomura and Chou[9] provided tighter bounds using a self-consistent approach. Also, Tsai[10] proposed a procedure to predict the shear modulus using contiguity factor which is a measure of the randomness of fiber packing. Lately, Kondo and Aoki[11] predicted the longitudinal shear modulus by establishing a random model.

But, most of those available methods do not accurately account for the effects of the shape and array of the reinforced fibers. However, it has been recognized from recent numerical[12,13] studies on fiber-reinforced composites that the effective shear moduli can be very sensitive to both cross-sectional shape and array of the reinforcing phases. In general, the effective longitudinal shear modulus from theoretical and numerical prediction[11,13] is higher in rectangular array than in hexagonal array of fibers. Although the hexagonal array is considered to be more representative of actual material geometry than the rectangular array,

* Currently at Jeonju University, Dept. of Mechanical Eng., Jeonju, Jeonbuk, Korea.

this fact can be attributed that the actual unidirectional composites have a randomly distributed fibers. Also, it is found that the shape of fibers shows the different reinforcing effects of the stress distribution and transfer around the fibers

In this paper, the longitudinal shear modulus of unidirectional continuous fiber-reinforced composite is predicted by theoretical and numerical analysis(FEA) methods that based on a concept of unit cell. The considered shapes of reinforced fiber are circular, hexagonal and rectangular. And the fiber spatial distribution is rectangular and hexagonal array. Those predicted moduli are compared with the measured data by modified isopescu shear test(IST) proposed by Adams and Walrath[14,15]. And the obtained longitudinal shear modulus(LSM) is discussed in aspects of the effects of fiber shapes and several proposed predictions.

A THEORETICAL MODEL

The composite model and the fiber type that used for theoretical and numerical methods are shown in Fig. 1. The cell types are classified as cell-0(rectangular array) for no interaction between the neighboring fibers, as cell-1(rectangular array) and as cell-2(hexagonal array) for considering an interaction between the fibers in y-direction only.

Fig. 1. Schematic of Unidirectional Composites Containing a Fiber in Elastic Matrix.

Fig. 2 shows the theoretical model of unit cell subjected to longitudinal shear loading with different fiber geometries. As shown in figure, the fiber direction is z-direction and the distance between fibers is a . To improve the accuracy of this analysis, the matrix area is divided into several section as shown.

Fig. 2. Theoretical Model of Unit Cell Subjected to Longitudinal Shear Loading.

The theoretical model has been developed based on the following assumptions, 1) perfect bonding between fiber and matrix , 2) matrix deform elastically but fiber is a rigid body and 3) fibers are distributed uniformly throughout the composite. Then LSM can be calculated from the strain energy and shear strain from displacement in the fiber direction at $y=a$. The total strain energy and stress in the elastic body of composite can be expressed as

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \int_v \sigma_{ij} \gamma_{ij} dv$$

$$\sigma_{yz} = G_{yz, avg} \times \gamma_{yz}$$

Then, the average strain energy within this unit cell regardless of fiber shape can be expressed as

$$U_o = 1/2 \gamma_{yz,avg}^2 G_{yz,avg} \quad \text{where } \gamma_{yz,avg} = \Delta/a$$

and the stored strain energy in the unit volume is $u_o = U_o/a^2$.

For the circular fiber shape, the matrix area is divided into 5 sections as shown in Fig. 2(a) to improve this analysis. After obtaining the average shear strain of each section, LSM can be obtained from

$$G_{avg} = G_m \left[2 \sum_{x_i=0}^r \left(\frac{1}{a-r-\sqrt{r^2-x_i^2}} \frac{r}{n} \right) + \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{(2a-r)(a-2r)}{a(a-r)} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{4} (a-2r)r \left\{ \left(\frac{(2a-r)}{a(a-r)} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{1}{a} \right)^2 \right\} \right]$$

where a is a length of unit cell, r is a radius of fiber and n is a stepsize

For the hexagonal fiber shape(Fig. 2(b)), the matrix area is divided into 6 sections to improve this analysis. Then LSM can be calculated as

$$G_{avg} = G_m \left[\left(\frac{1}{a/l-\sqrt{3}} \right) + \left(\frac{4l}{4a-3\sqrt{3}l} \right) + \frac{1}{2} (a-\sqrt{3}l) \left(\frac{a}{2} - l \right) \left(\frac{1}{a} + \frac{2}{2a-\sqrt{3}l} \right)^2 + \sqrt{3}l \left(\frac{a}{2} - l \right) \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{2a} + \frac{1}{2a-\sqrt{3}l} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{4a^2} \right\} \right]$$

For the rectangular fiber shape(Fig. 2(c)), the matrix area is divided into 3 sections to improve this analysis. Then LSM can be calculated as

$$G_{avg} = G_m \left[\left(\frac{1}{a/l-1} \right) + \left(1 - \frac{l}{2a} \right)^2 + \frac{l(a-l)}{4a^2} \right]$$

A FE model using 8 noded quadrilateral elements is used to evaluate the shear modulus. The displacement controlled computations were performed by the general purpose FE program, ANSYS 5.0. : $w = .0005 \text{ mm}$, $w = .001 \text{ mm}$, $w = .002 \text{ mm}$, $w = .003 \text{ mm}$, $w = .005 \text{ mm}$, $w = .008 \text{ mm}$ and $w = .01 \text{ mm}$. If u , v and w are the displacement in the x , y and z directions respectively, The used boundary conditions were $u=v=w=0$ along the $y=0$ plane and $u=v=0$,

$w=w(x,y)$ along the $y=a$ plane. The material properties used in this analysis are $E_f=220$ GPa, $\nu_f=0.25$ for reinforcement and $E_m= 3.0$ GPa, $\nu_m=0.33$ for matrix. Here, E is Young's modulus and ν is Poisson's ratio. Then the LSM can be calculated as

$$G_{avg.} = \frac{\sigma_{yz}}{\left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{w_i}{b} \right]} \quad y = b$$

where n is the number of node and w_i is the displacement in z -direction.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The matrix used in this study is epoxy that mixed resin with hardener by 5 to 1, both obtained from Jungdo Chemical Inc.(Type JEC-880). The reinforced materials is carbon fiber (ACELAN, Type TZ-307, Taekwang Ind. Co. Ltd.). Plaques were produced by curing the poured epoxy in a molding box that arranged with the fibers. Both room and high(up to 50 °C) temperatures were used to eliminate the bubbles within the sample in several curing steps. The fiber volume fraction was regulated by number of wined fibers in molding box(9 and 21 vol. %). Individual specimen was cut from the panels with the fibers oriented in the longitudinal direction using a diamond wheel saw that can prevent specimen from debonding and micro-cracking. The test specimen geometry of IST is 75 mm length x 22 mm height x 6 mm thickness. The notch depth is 10% of the specimen height with a 90° notch centered along the specimen length.. The specimen is placed in the fixture by assuring alignment and centering of the notch. The testing machine is Shimadzu Autograph (Model:AG-5000E) tensile machine. Specimen instrumented with 45° strain gage centered in the middle section was loaded monotonically to failure at crosshead speed of 1 mm/min. The measurement of shear modulus required to determine the shear strain corresponding to the average shear stress across the test section. To measure the strain, the multichannel system(Model AS1302, NEC San-ei Instruments, Ltd) is used by connecting with tensile machine.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

All tests were performed in room temperature and repeated more than three times to assure the accurate data.

Fig. 3. The Typical Stress-Strain Curves.

Fig.4. SEM of Fracture Surface

Fig. 3 shows the typical stress-strain curve for the tested samples. The fibers are oriented perpendicular to the cross-section and distributed inhomogeneously. Fig. 4 shows SEM micrographs of the typical fracture surfaces under longitudinal shear stress with 21 vol.% fiber content. Some fibers are broken and debonded from matrix when the weak matrix cracks. A clean fiber surface with a small matrix residue means very weak interface bonding between the fibers and the matrix. This results in a low fiber strength transfer to matrix.

The calculated LSM as a function of fiber volume fraction is shown in Figs. 5(a), 5(b) and 5(c).

Fig. 5(a) G_{yz} - V_f Relation for Circular Fiber Shape.

Fig. 5(b) G_{yz} - V_f Relation for Hexagonal Fiber Shape

Fig. 5(c). G_{yz} - V_f Relation for Rectangular Fiber Shape.

These curves shows that LSM value in lower fiber volume content is in the order of rectangular, circular and hexagonal fiber shape even though difference is quite small. But, for the higher fiber volume content(above 40%), LSM is in the order of circle, hexagonal and rectangular fiber shape. This indicates that the fiber morphological distribution and the stress transfer play a very important role on elastic shear properties of unidirectional composites.

Figs. 5(a), 5(b) and 5(c) also compare the theoretical prediction available in the literature[8,9] with LSM of actual composites in the case of glass-epoxy and carbon-epoxy composites. It is found that the measured LSM in this study is in good agreement with the published data as shown. also gives a good agreement with the theoretical predictions in low volume.

It should be also noted that theoretical prediction for circle fiber is inside Hashin's prediction [8] and Nomura & Chou improved low bound[9]. But, all finite element analysis data fall outside of both predictions especially in low fiber volume fraction. This can be due to difficulty in load transfer to matrix from loading point. For hexagonal and rectangular fiber shapes, all present predictions and experimental data show good agreement. The experimental data of carbon fiber reinforced composite fraction as we tested.

Differences in the extent of load transfer between the matrix and reinforcement contribute to the dependence of the effective LSM on the shapes of the reinforcement. Fig. 6(a) and 6(b) show the stress distribution in z-direction at $y=0.5$ mm of unit cell for $V_f=10\%$ and 30% when there is a fiber-direction displacement of $w=0.01$ mm. As shown in Fig. 6(a) for $V_f=10\%$, the stress transfer between fibers does happen more easily for rectangular fiber shape than for circular and hexagonal fiber shapes. But for higher fiber volume fraction at $V_f=30\%$ of Fig.6(b), the stress transfer does happen more easily for circular fiber shape especially in the middle range than any other fiber types. This also agrees with higher LSM of rectangular fiber shape in low fiber volume fraction and circular fiber shape in higher fiber volume fraction. These facts can be looked at unit cell geometries. When the unit cell has a constant fiber volume fraction and rectangular array as cell-1 type, the distance in the middle of unit cell is quite different for each type of fiber. If the rectangular fiber shape has a distance of a , then this distance for circular fiber shape will be $1.1284a$ and for hexagonal fiber shape will be $1.0746a$ respectively. Based on this length, LSM should be in the order of circular,

hexagonal and rectangular fiber shapes. This agrees well with the case of higher fiber volume fraction. But the stress distribution around the fibers and stress transfer in the matrix seem to be more important for lower fiber volume fraction.

However, constrained matrix shearing can also influence the stiffening of the composite. By comparing the numerical data in Figs. 5(a), 5(b) and 5(c), it is found that the effective LSM for the hexagonal array is lower than that for the rectangular array of fibers. The difference is large at higher fiber volume fraction while it is small at lower fiber volume fraction. This also agrees well with the published data[7,10]. Recently, Ravichandran[3] shows that even the transverse elastic modulus for the rectangular array is higher than that for the hexagonal array of fibers based on the FEA analysis using the experimental works of Prewo[17]. In the aspects of LSM, all the present predictions and experimental data fit well with published data of LSM except for the circular cross-section fiber.

Fig. 6. Stress Distribution for Different Fiber Geometry Types at $y=0.5$ mm: (a) for $V_f=10\%$ and (b) for $V_f=30\%$.

CONCLUSION

It has been found that the shape of the reinforced fiber has a significant effect on the overall shear modulus of the composites for a fixed concentration and properties of the constituent phases. Among the different reinforcement shapes considered in this study, the rectangular shape shows the highest effective LSM at a lower fiber volume fraction while the circular shape shows the highest value at a high fiber volume content. This can be explained by considering the geometrical distribution of unit cell and stress transfer between the fibers and the matrix. As constrained matrix shearing influences the stiffening of the composite, the spatial distribution of the constituent phases of the composite has a pronounced effect on the overall LSM. It is found that the effective LSM for the hexagonal array is lower than that for the rectangular array of fibers. The difference is large at higher fiber volume fraction while it is small at lower fiber volume fraction.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This research was supported by the Korea Science & Engineering Foundation Research Grant in 1994. We would like to thank for their financial supports.

REFERENCES

1. T. Mura, *Micromechanics of Defects in Solids*, 2nd Edition, Martinis Nijhoff, The Hague, (1987)
2. R. M. Christensen, *Mechanics of Composite Materials*, Wiley, New York,(1979).
3. K. S. Ravichandran, "A Simple Model of Deformation Behavior of Two Phase Composites", *Acta Metall. Mat.* **42**, 1113-1123,(1994).
4. J. Morton, H. Ho and M. Y. Tsai, An Evaluation of the Iosipescu Specimen for Composite Materials Shear Property Measurement, *J. of Comp. Mat.*, **26**, 708-750.(1992).
5. Marek-Jerzy Pindera, G. Choksi, A Methodology for Accurate Shear Characterization of Unidirectional Composites, *J. of Comp. Mat.*, Vol. 21, 1164-1184,(1987).
6. T. W. Chou, S. Nomura, and M. Taya, A Self-Consistent Approach to the Elastic Stiffness of Short-Fiber Composites, *J. of Comp. Mat.*, Vol. 14, 178-188,(1980).
7. I. M. Ward and A. P. Wilczynski, Bounds for the Elastic Constants of a Unidirectional Fibre Composite: A New Approach, *J. of Mat. Sci.*, Vol. 28, 1973-1977,(1993).
8. Z. Hashin and B. W. Rosen, The Elastic Moduli of Fiber-Reinforced Materials, *J. of Appl. Mech.*, Vol. 31E, 223-229,(1964).
9. S. Nomura and T. W. Chou, Bound of Effective Thermal Conductivity of Short Fiber Composites, *J. of Comp. Mat.*, Vol. 14, 120-129,(1980).
10. S. W. Tsai, Structural Behavior of Composite Material, NASA CR-71,1(1971).
11. K. Kondo and T. Aoki, Longitudinal Shear Modulus of Unidirectional Composites, *Prog. in Scien. and Engg. of Composites*, Hayashi, Kawata & Umekawa Ed. ICCM-IV, Tokyo, 357-364,(1982).
12. Y. L. Shen, M. Finot, A Needleman and S. Suresh, Effective Elastic Response of Two-Phase Composites, *Acta. Metall. Mater.* Vol. 42, No. 1, 77-97,(1994).
13. T. H. Jeong and D. J. Lee, Effects of Fiber Morphology on Shear Modulus of Continuous Fiber-Reinforced Composites, *J. the Inst. of Industrial Tech.*, Vol. 22, No. 2, 51-59,(1994).
14. D. E. Walrath and D. F. Adams, The Iosipescu Shear Test as Applied to Composite", *Experi. Mech.*, March, 105-110,(1983).
15. D. E. Walrath and D. F. Adams, Further Development of the Iosipescu Shear Test Method, *Experi. Mech.*, June, 113-119,(1987).
16. T. H. Jeong and D. J. Lee, Longitudinal Shear Modulus for Continuous Fiber-Reinforced Composites, *Proc. in Korean Soc. Mech. Engg. Fall Conf.*, Suwon, Nov. 4-5, (1994).
17. K. M. Prewo and K. G. Kreider, Boron Reinforced Aluminum Systems, *Mat. Tech. Ser.* Vol. 6,38-44,(1973).